

FORMATION OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE OF THE TEACHER AS AN ONE OF THE MAIN TASKS OF MODERN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The creation of teachers' professional competence in the context of society's digitization is examined in the article. The creation of teachers' professional competence in the context of society's digitization is examined in the essay. The stages of the development of teachers' professional information competence are provided at the same time as an analysis of information competence ideas.

INTRODUCTION

The demands on a teacher's professional development, particularly in terms of their degree of professional competence, are rising in the context of the shift to a modern information society. The information and communication complex is one of a teacher's most crucial professional qualities nowadays. In the writings of V. F. Burmakina, I. N. Falina, O. N. Shilova, O. V. Ursova, A. A. Elizarov, M. S. Tsvetkova, L. N. Gorbunova, A. M. Semibratov, and F.M. Z., the idea of "information and communication competence of a teacher" was taken into consideration. Many scientists mention the following factors while discussing the potential of information and communication technologies for the educational process (L. L. Bosova, V. A. Krasilnikov, E. I. Mashbitz, I. V. Robert, A. A. Abdukadyrova, F.M. Zakirova, N.

- the development of student-centered learning, additional and advanced education; the expansion of e-learning; the independence of the educational process from the place and time of training; the creation of a unified information and educational environment for learning not only one region, but the nation and the global community as a whole; the unlimited possibilities of collecting, storing, transferring, transforming, analyzing, and using information of various nature;

Increased subject activity in the organization of the educational process; Significantly improved methodological and software support for the educational process; Ensuring the Possibility of Choosing an Individual Training Path; Development of Student's Independent

Search Activity; Increased Student Activity in the Organization of the Educational Process; Significantly improved Organizational Support of the Educational Process (Virtual Schools, Laboratories, Universities, etc.); The school development strategy determines the primary objectives of modern school informatization, which include supplying educational and organizational processes with new types of information resources based on the use of computer networks and their information content, as well as new information and technology.

Many educational professionals are now behind in their capacity to operate in the area of utilizing information technology's capabilities in the educational process. The majority of instructors' lack of readiness to integrate information and communication technology into a general education school's instructional process is one of the primary causes. The characteristics of the process of building teachers' professional competence in the area of utilizing information and communication technology in the educational process are determined by the quickly evolving field of information technology.

A subject teacher's information and communication competence at the contemporary stage is defined as his readiness and capacity to use contemporary information and communication technologies in pedagogical activities to address a variety of educational issues and create strategies for raising qualifications in this field. The instructor, who possesses information and communication skills, not only aims to use computers in his job but also models and creates contemporary technologies.

Materials and Methods

By considerably enhancing a teacher's professional capacities and broadening the parameters of his pedagogical culture, the use of information and pedagogical technology enhances the efficacy of his professional activities. Based on the following fundamental electronic didactic functions, information technology:

1) visibility, which promotes awareness and significance of the perceived educational information, the development of ideas, and concepts; 2) informativeness, since teaching aids are direct sources of knowledge, that is, they are carriers of specific information; 3) compensating, encouraging learning and helping to reach the objective with the least amount of time and effort. 4) adaptation, which is concerned with upholding suitable circumstances for the course of the learning process, planning demonstrations, autonomous work, and the continuity of information; 5) Integrability, which enables us to analyze an entity or phenomena in both its parts and its entirety

Focusing on cognitive (independent study of the material while interacting with computer tools) and developmental technologies (problem and programmed learning), as well as the tools that support them (electronic textbooks and teaching aids), is advised during the early stages of the formation of a teacher's information competence. This does not imply that other technologies should not be employed at this point, but rather that cognitive and developmental technologies will be successful and help learners the most given their unique characteristics. The basic step of the development of a professional identity is the following level. Technologies that are effective at this level should be viewed as activity- and development-related (analysis of professional tasks, professionally oriented research activities, problem solving).

Computer resources such as expert training systems, network resources, and simulators that can support the technologies of this stage. The last level of training is the one when a specialist's competency is developed. Technology that is effective at this stage should be characterized as personality-oriented (independent learning, independent research, anticipatory work, projective learning, training according to an individual plan), developmental (role-playing games, reflection on professional activity, problem-solving in interaction, searching and generating new professional knowledge). The following organizational and educational prerequisites must be met before instructors may be prepared to use information technology in pedagogical activities: Modernization of the school's methodological work as the foundation for organizing the educational process of school teachers for the use of information technology in professional activities; a system of lifelong learning as the primary condition for the formation of the readiness of school students to use information technology; development of a single information and educational space of the school based on the system integration of information technology into all links of the educational process;

The following goals are in line with the topic and target of the work: 1) to investigate the school's computer technology infrastructure and ensure its efficient usage in the educational process. 2) Examine how teachers' information and communication skills are developed and improved; 3) Identify the primary issues and development strategies for teachers' information and communication skills. The following techniques were employed to complete the assigned tasks and reach the designated goal: 1) a critical-constructive study of the research problem's literature; 2) the use of observation as a linguistic and methodological tool; and 3) a learning experiment

The creation of the requisite pedagogical conditions that contribute to the improvement of the teacher's pedagogical skills, as well as his inclusion in active activities based on the use of information and communication technology in the educational process, should be given priority in the system for organizing the teacher's lifelong learning of information technologies. By "technologies based on the use of computing and other information technology, as well as specialized software, information and methodological support," specialists refer to information technologies in education.

According to author E.V. Ivanova, when we refer to a teacher's information and communication competency, we are referring to their system of knowledge and abilities for using information technologies in a way that effectively addresses professional pedagogical issues. In the current climate of educational modernization, there are several strategic considerations for a teacher's development of information and communication skills. These considerations include: improving professional competence; being able to work in an informational and educational environment; being tolerant, sociable, and cooperative; being able to interact in a network; being ready to continue learning throughout one's life; and being able to put knowledge acquired into practice.

Today, virtually all educational institutions have corporate and municipal networks, contemporary personal computers, and websites that are accessible over the Internet. The state initiatives that have been undertaken with the aim of developing the nation's educational informatization have greatly aided in the development of the information

environment in general education schools. Therefore, having simply subject-methodological and psychological-pedagogical training is insufficient for teachers in the modern world. The increased adoption of computers in society and their active integration into the educational process make it necessary for teachers to be knowledgeable in information technology.

Information and communication competence is one of the aspects of professional maturity that a teacher develops when they study computers and use information technology as a teaching tool in their professional activity. The following levels of the development of information and communication competence can be distinguished by study of the teacher's educational activity: 1) The amount of information consumption; 2) The level of computer usage; 3) The level of logical functioning and equipment knowledge; 4) The level of subject-specific activities based on an innovative, interdisciplinary approach.

Using Microsoft Power Point to create presentations 1. PowerPoint experience. 2. Creating a PowerPoint that includes a table and a diagram. 3. When showing, adding images and animations to a slide. 4. Designing command buttons. 5. Archiving and setting up a demonstration of a presentation.

Microsoft Word, second. Font and size. 2. Making and changing a text file. 3. Keyboarding and modifying text. 4. Spacing and indents for paragraphs.

5. Formatting tables and creating them. adding a figure; 6. Page numbers are 7. the completed manuscript being printed. Microsoft Publisher, third 1. Getting a postcard ready. 2. Creating and publishing booklets. Internet, fourth 1. A web search. 2. Email. V. Using information technology to create lesson plans.

DISCUSSION

It was possible to delve deeper into the core of the examined pedagogical phenomenon and the related processes through the analysis of diagnostic data, allowing for the development and justification of pedagogical conclusions as well as the creation of forecasts for the continued growth of this quality. In particular, it enables us to evaluate how well organizational initiatives shape a teacher's information competence within the framework of a regional system of supplementary professional education. The experiment's ascertaining and forming phases, which involved statistical data processing, revealed a consistent correlation between the pedagogical conditions for the development of the teacher's information competence created during the educational process and the upward trend of indicators of the advancement of this complex teacher education. Thus, both average values and values for component values significantly rise in the experimental groups. Comparative investigation revealed that the way instructional activities are organized has a favorable impact on how a teacher develops this quality.

There is a connection between teaching and informative activity, or, to put it another way, the teacher's personal competences, which were developed via informational activity, start to show up not just in his or her professional work but also serve as a moral compass in other areas of his or her life. The following are the prerequisites for a teacher's ability to develop information and communication skills in the educational system: (1) a scientifically based organization of the process; (2) actualization of the teacher's subjective position in the process of working with information; (3) a special organization of an informational educational professionally significant environment; and (4) stimulation of the motivating

factors. monitoring, the focus of which is the teacher's degree of informational proficiency. The teachers were requested to try their hand at themselves at the conclusion of the trial and presented a master class on learning these programs.

CONCLUSION

The use of Microsoft Power Point, Windows Movie Maker, and Acoolsoft PPT2Video Converter increases students' interest in using ICT in both academic and extracurricular settings for grades 6 through 9. These programs can make our lessons even more interesting, which will aid students in learning new material on academic subjects. Based on the analysis of professional activity and the definition of its new functions, develop a model of teacher competence. The new educational environment places a demand on such teacher competencies as design and construction, organizational and technological, communicative and regulatory, technical and didactic, etc. that are currently underdeveloped in him. Following a review of the educational system, the following standards for a teacher's information and communication skills were created: 2) The capacity to interact with electronic information and present it in various formats (text, table, figure, etc.); 3) The capacity to carry out efficient information search, selection, and presentation using Internet resources; 4) The capacity to conduct lectures, seminars, and discussions using telecommunication technologies; and 5) The capacity to use information technology. According to system specifications, a modern teacher needs the following work abilities for successful educational activity: 1) With text editors to create and execute texts of different complexity; 2) With spreadsheets to process numerical data and display it as diagrams, graphs, etc. 3) using presentation technologies to create a visual presentation of instructional content for everyone; 4) using graphic media editors to process images and create multimedia products; 5) using e-mail, telecommunications, and Internet technologies to communicate with students and colleagues around the world; and 6) using cutting-edge information retrieval systems to look up academic and scientific literature. The following assignments were set by the schools as part of the general education system requirements: Extensive technological resources, Internet access for educational institutions; 2) development of a local electronic network within each school, linking the operations of all school structures; 3) development of specialized computer training programs for educators; 4) establishment of local pages in school libraries and information centers with electronic teaching resources from educators and links to online educational resources; 5) web support for academic subjects; and 6) creation of electronic textbooks with multimedia didactic materials.

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